

Supplementary Materials

Tomáš Prostějovský^{a,I}, Lucie Spáčilová^{a,II}, Martin Reli^{a,III}, Radim Žebrák^b, and Kamila Kočí^{a,IV*}

*^aInstitute of Environmental Technology, Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies,
VSB – Technical University of Ostrava, 17. listopadu 2172/15, Ostrava-Poruba, 708 00,
Czech Republic*

^bDekonta Inc., Dřetovice 109, Stehelčevy, 273 42, Czech Republic

^IORCID: 0000-0002-5796-3022

^{II}ORCID: 0009-0008-6442-3033

^{III}ORCID: 0000-0002-4003-0234

^{IV}ORCID: 0000-0001-6682-7404

Figure S1 pH values in the tubular reactor R3 for different air flows and initial ammonia concentration 50 ppmv.

Figure S2 Average ammonia amount in the tubular reactor R3 shown as nitrogen amount after 1 hour.

The series of tests

Changes in nitrogen concentration (a) and pH (b) were monitored at half-hourly intervals. Full colored columns are concentrations of nitrogen from ammonia and stripes columns are concentration of nitrogen from NO_3^- . Nitrites are not shown in the graph because their amount was below the limit of determination.

Figure S3 Effect of different elements on the photodegradation of ammonia - a) total nitrogen amount (TN), b) pH.

Surprisingly, none of the above conditions had a significant impact on the degradation of ammonia (a) and the same effect, or rather no effect, can be observed for pH (b).

The following formula was used to calculate the values in Table S1:

$$E_{EO} = \frac{P}{F \cdot \log \frac{c_{in}}{c_{out}}}$$

The cost of the solution used per hour of experiment operation was calculated from the following data:

Solution volume	0.191 m ³		
Water cost (CZ, 2024)	109.47 CZK/m ³	4.68	EUR/m ³
Sum of water cost		0.83	EUR/experiment

No KOH exp.

Hydrogen peroxide (2 dm ³)	292 CZK	2.32	EUR/h
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KOH exp.

Hydrogen peroxide (0.155 dm ³)	22.63 CZK	0.18	EUR/h
KOH (37.1 g)	4.67 CZK	0.04	EUR/h

Table S1 E_{EO} and calculated costs for the flow rate 113 m³ · h⁻¹ (**F**) and inlet ammonia concentration 50 ppmv (**c_{in}**) with and without KOH addition.

Type of experiment	Average conc. after R1 (c_{out})	Lamps in R1 (P)	E_{EO} R1	Cost of 1 m ³ treatment	Average outlet conc. after R2 (c_{out})	Lamps in R1 + R3 + pump (P)	E_{EO} R1+R2+R3	Cost of solution	Cost of 1-h. treatment	Cost of 1 m ³ treatment
(-)	(ppmv)	(kW)	(kWh · m ⁻³ · order ⁻¹)	(€ · m ⁻³)	(ppmv)	(kW)	(kWh · m ⁻³ · order ⁻¹)	(€ · h ⁻¹)	(€ · h ⁻¹)	(€ · m ⁻³)
Without KOH	31.5	0.32	0.014	0.002	2.0	1.29	0.008	3.157	3.268	0.029
With KOH	31.5	0.32	0.014	0.002	7.5*	1.29	0.014	1.050	1.238	0.011

* The increased ammonia concentration at the outlet during experiments with KOH addition was caused by the higher volatility of ammonia from the solution due to the elevated pH value. Paradoxically, the cost of experiments with KOH was more than 2.5 times lower. The reason was the use of a smaller amount of peroxide compared to the experiments without KOH addition.